

Vocabulary Learning as the Predictor of Third-Grader EFL Learners' Achievement: A Case for Translation

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to formulate a model to predict the performance of Iranian high school third-graders on the End of the Course Achievement (ECA) tests through their performance on the vocabulary tests, which were administered throughout the course. To meet this end, thirty two learners – aging seventeen to nineteen, all male – participated in the study which took nine months to complete. Their linguistic abilities were approximately at Intermediate-Mid level according to the ACTFL proficiency guidelines (1998). The sampling procedure was the intact group method. 333 lexical items were taught to the learners in the decontextualized paired-associate translation method. The classes were held two hours a week in a nine-month course of time. Six sets of vocabulary tests were administered and every learner's average was calculated. The learners' scores on the ECA tests and their average scores on the vocabulary tests were analyzed through the regression analysis procedure to derive a model that could reliably predict the learners' ECA scores through their average performance on the vocabulary scores. The analysis yielded the following formula: $(\text{AVERAGE VOCABULARY} \times 0.713) + 2.871 \pm [3.1]$.

Keywords: Vocabulary Learning, Explicit Vocabulary Instruction, Translation, Lexical Knowledge Transfer, Reading Comprehension, Regression Analysis, Achievement Prediction.

1. Introduction

“Translation in language teaching has been treated as a pariah in almost all the fashionable high-profile language teaching theories of the 20th century” (G. Cook, 2010. p. xv). Nevertheless it has been commonly used in a variety of contexts around the world (Benson, 2000). It has been the norm at university-level language teaching (Malmkjær, 2004).

Translation method of vocabulary teaching is currently the most widely used method in Iranian high schools. The research on translation as a method of vocabulary teaching indicates that it is one of the most reliable and efficient methods of lexical instruction (Hayati and Mohammadi 2009; Jahangard, 2007b; Laufer and Girsai, 2008; Laufer and Shmueli ,1997; Lotto and de Groot,1998; Mehrpour, 2008; Prince, 1996; Ramachandran and Rahim , 2004).

During the twelve years of teaching EFL at high schools, the teacher/researcher of the present study felt that those learners who were successful vocabulary learners under the translation method were successful in the summative achievement tests which were routinely administered by the Ministry of Education, as well. This, nevertheless, was a hunch and needed empirical research to examine it. Although numerous research studies examine the predictive power of vocabulary knowledge in anticipating the magnitude of reading ability (See, e.g., Gersten and Geva, 2003; Grabe , 1991; Laufer,1992; Nation,1990; Protopapas, A.& Sideridis, G.D.& Mouzaki, A.& Simos, P.G. (2007); Qian, 2002; Tannenbaum, K.R.& Torgesen, J.K.& Wagner, R.K. (2006) , to our knowledge, there are very few studies focusing on the power of second language vocabulary

knowledge, particularly gained through translation method, in predicting a learner's score on a future achievement test.

Taking the results of a recent research which showed that low proficiency learners are able to make practical use of their lexical knowledge learned through explicit methods of vocabulary teaching only if the induced involvement load of the learning tasks are large (Jahangard, A. and Moinzadeh, A. and Tavakoli, M. (2010), and the past research which indicates that there are high correlations between reading comprehension and vocabulary knowledge, the current researchers hypothesize that the vocabulary learning of the learners in the present study will provide a reliable prediction of the learners' achievement scores with a practically acceptable margin of error. The central question, then, is whether it is possible to obtain a formula that can reliably predict Iranian learners' End of the Course Achievement (ECA) scores through their vocabulary scores in Grade three of high school.

1.2. Literature Review

Interest in the relationship between vocabulary and reading comprehension has a long history in the research of L2/FL reading. Observing the performance of FL/L2 readers, confronted with unknown vocabulary, researchers have noted the important role of vocabulary as a predictor of overall reading ability (Grabe, 1991; Nation, 1990).

Related research and current educational practice suggests a correlation between students' vocabulary knowledge and their comprehension of what they read (Gersten and Geva, 2003). Similarly, Stahl (2003) says that the relationship between vocabulary and reading comprehension is a "robust" one and that vocabulary knowledge has consistently been the "foremost predictor of a text's difficulty" (p. 241). Stahl adds that vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension are strongly correlated, based on measurement of word difficulty and sentence difficulty (pp. 241-242). Qian (2002) contends that, "Scores on vocabulary size, depth of vocabulary knowledge, and reading comprehension are highly, and positively correlated; and scores on depth of vocabulary knowledge can make a unique contribution to the prediction of reading comprehension levels" (p. 280). Protopapas et al. (2007) report that any effects of decoding on comprehension may be mediated by the lexicon, consistent with the lexical quality hypothesis. They argue that skilled word reading influences comprehension by strengthening lexical representations, at least when phonological decoding can be relatively effortless.

In a similar vein, Tannenbaum et al. (2006) found that breadth has a stronger relationship to reading comprehension than does depth/fluency; however, the two dimensions of word knowledge have significant overlapping variance that contributes to the prediction of reading comprehension. Also, Laufer (1992) found that the lexical level in a second language is a better predictor of reading in L2 than the learners' general ability, predicting failure (when the learner's lexical level is lower than 3,000 word families), or success (when the level is over 5,000).

There are also research studies that demonstrate a significant relationship between lexical knowledge and course achievement. Regarding the relation of vocabulary and performance on multiple-choice achievement tests of college courses, Turner, H. and Williams, R.L. (2007) found that scores on a vocabulary test given at the beginning of two semesters in a large entry-level course predicted performance on multiple-choice exams more strongly than pre-course knowledge and critical thinking.

Despite the substantial body of research that confirms the relation of vocabulary with reading comprehension, speaking, and writing, there is a paucity of research concerning the learners' vocabulary development and its power to predict the learners' performance on the End of the Course Achievement (ECA) Tests that are routinely administered by the central offices of the Board of Education every year. The important point about these tests is that they consist of a variety of tasks which require not only reading comprehension skills, but also tap other linguistic systems

of knowledge such as orthographic, phonological, and syntactic competences. The characteristics of the ECA test used in the study are described more elaborately under the Method heading, and a copy of it is available in Appendix 3.

3. Method

3.1. Subjects

Thirty-two learners in Grade three (aged 17-19) learning English as foreign language participated in the study. They were Farsi (Persian) native speakers, who had studied English for four years prior to the experiment. Their linguistic ability was comparable to the sub-competencies described by the ACTFL proficiency guidelines (1998) for Intermediate-Mid level. Moreover, all the learners were studying Physics/Mathematics as their major field of study.

3.2. Materials and Procedures

Three hundred and thirty three lexical items included in the English textbook, namely, Birjandy, P. & Norouzi, M. & Mahmoody, G. (2004). *English Book Three*, which is routinely assigned by the Ministry of Education for EFL teaching in Iranian public high schools in Grade three were taught to the participants in the present study. The book typically includes sections of reading comprehension, grammar, pronunciation practice, dialogues, and a list of new words (with no explanation of meaning or synonyms) in the ending part of each lesson. These wordlists (See Appendix 1) were used for vocabulary instruction and subsequent vocabulary testing in the study. To save space, the number of the new words in each lesson is presented in Table 1 below:

Table 1
The Number of Words and Lessons in Book Three

Lesson	Number of New Words and Expressions
1	60
2	52
3	55
4	68
5	46
6	52
Total Number of Words	333

Lexical instruction was conducted in a uniform method throughout the classes which took nine months to complete. The classes were conducted in the following manner: First, the researcher/teacher pronounced three times the individual words in the word list of each lesson clearly and the learners were asked to repeat them aloud and simultaneously write them (in Farsi transcription for purposes of speed and convenience, and also because many of the learners were not familiar enough with the English phonetic alphabet to use it) beside the orthographic form of the words which were available in their textbooks. Then, in the second step, after the pronunciation was done, the vocabulary list was examined again, this time with regard to meaning. It is worthy of notice that, for polysemous words, only those meaning(s) for which the words were used in the book was/were given, and the additional meanings were omitted from the instructional procedure. To clarify the meaning of the new words, the L1 equivalents of the new words were provided by the researcher/teacher orally two times with pauses between each repetition to give the learners enough time to write them for later practice. Cautious attempts were made on the part of the teacher/researcher to provide translation equivalents that were relatively most congruent with the target words in terms of semantic and syntactic features. Syntactic features that were most emphasized and highlighted for the learners were those of grammatical category, tense, and case.

Lastly, for further rehearsal purposes and consolidating the target words, the learners were assigned additional homework wherein they were required to write the corresponding orthographic and phonological forms of the words six times after the preliminary instructional session was over. Appropriate completion of the homework assignments was closely monitored by the teacher/researcher at the beginning of all of the class sessions throughout the course. In cases where a learner failed to do them or was not cooperative enough, besides motivating strategies, a variety of punishment measures were adopted including giving negative marks in their score records, or having them write twice as much of the undone assignments, or sending them to the authorities of the school for additional penalties, or calling their parents to school.

Immediately after the introduction of the new words to the students and the monitoring of the homework assignments in the subsequent class (usually a week after), the vocabulary tests (See Appendix 2) - always with one week advance announcement - were administered.

The test development and scoring procedures were as follows: Ten lexical items from the wordlists of the related lessons were randomly selected to be included in the vocabulary tests. The test items were in fact the Farsi translations of the target English words in the previously memorized wordlists for which the learners had to provide the following lexical features: orthographic, phonological, and syntactic (i.e. category, tense, and case, depending on the lexical items grammatical properties). However, since the grammatical features of the words that the learners supplied as answers, could be logically inferred by the researcher/rater in the majority of the cases, the students were not obliged to demonstrate them explicitly in the answer-sheets.

As to the scoring procedure, 0.5 of a unit of score was allocated to each of the lexical features in the given lexical items; thus, two points for every lexical item which, on the whole, amounted to a total score of twenty in every vocabulary test.

The procedures of lexical instruction and vocabulary testing continued up to the end of the course when the book content was exhausted. Lastly, near to the end of the academic year, the students took the End of the Course Achievement (ECA) exams (See Appendix 3) the major objectives of which were to make a holistic assessment concerning the achievement of the pre-specified course objectives. These tests are usually designed, standardized, and administered either directly by the central offices of the Ministry of Education, or indirectly by the teachers at the local schools. However, no matter who develops them, they follow a uniform scheme or format which is mandated by the officials of the Ministry of Education.

The reliability indexes obtained from the batteries utilized in the study are presented in Tables 2 below.

Table 2
Reliability Indexes of the Measures Used in Grade Three

Grade	Test Type	Reliability Index (Cronbach's Alpha on Standardized Items)
2	Vocab. Test Lesson 1	.88
2	Vocab. Test Lesson 2	.89
2	Vocab. Test Lesson 3	.90
2	Vocab. Test Lesson 4	.88
2	Vocab. Test Lesson 5	.52
2	Vocab. Test Lesson 6	.82
2	ECA Test	.71

3.3. Data Analysis

The mean score of every learner on the vocabulary tests was calculated. Then, through the statistical procedure of regression analysis, the data from the mean scores and the ECA exam scores were analyzed to derive a model which could reliably predict the learners' performance on the ECA exam.

To check whether the two variables of the ECA exam and the average vocabulary were suitable for linear regression, its scatter plot was examined. The resulting scatter plot (Figure 1) seemed to be sufficient for linear regression.

Figure 1. Scatter plot of ECA exam by average vocabulary in Grade Three

4. Results and Discussion

Table 3 below demonstrates the coefficients of the regression line. It shows that the expected ECA exam score is equal to $(\text{AVERAGE VOCAB} \times 0.713) + 2.871$. For example, if a student earns an average score of 15 on the vocabulary tests during the course, the expected ECA exam for him/her would be: $(15 \times .713) + 2.871 = 13.566$.

Table 3
Coefficients (^a) of the Regression Line for Grade Three

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.871	3.331		.862	.396

	AVERAGE VOCAB.	.713	.204	.551	3.491	.002
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a. Dependent Variable: ECA Exam

The ANOVA table below (Table 4) tests the acceptability of the model from a statistical perspective. The amount of regression sums of squares is 122.385 indicating that about 33 percent of the total variation is explained by the model and the amount of residual sums of squares is 281.134 showing that about 67 percent of the variation is due to some factors other than the average vocabulary variable. The significance value of the F statistic is less than 0.05, which means that the variation explained by the model is not due to chance.

Table 4
 ANOVA (^b) for Grade Three

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	122.385	1	122.385	12.189	.002(a)
	Residual	281.134	28	10.040		
	Total	403.519	29			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Average Vocabulary

b. Dependent Variable: ECA Exam

However, while the ANOVA table is a useful test of the model's ability to explain any variation in the dependent variable, it does not directly address the strength of that relationship. The model summary in Table 5 reports the strength of the relationship between the model and the dependent variable, i.e., ECA exam. The multiple correlation coefficient, *R*, which is the linear correlation between the observed and the model-predicted values of the dependent variable is .551. *R Square*, which is also called the coefficient of determination, is .303 showing that approximately 30 percent of the variation in ECA exam is explained by the model. Its interpretation is that 30 percent of the variation in the ECA test scores is common with the vocabulary scores. The *Standard Error of the Estimate* of the model is approximately 3.16 out of a total of 30, meaning that the prediction model produces an error range between $\pm [3.16]$. Therefore, the prediction formula must be rewritten as $(\text{AVERAGE VOCAB} \times 0.713) + 2.871 \pm [3.16]$.

Table 5
 Model Fit Summary (^b) for Grade Three

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.551(a)	.303	.278	3.16867

a. Predictors: (Constant), Average Vocabulary

b. Dependent Variable: ECA Exam

Conclusion

The results showed that vocabulary learning through translation pairs can function as a substantial predictor of the learners' performance on the End of the Course Achievement exams among the learners in Grade three of Iranian public high schools. The formula which was derived from the regression analysis was $(\text{AVERAGE VOCAB} \times 0.713) + 2.871 \pm [3.16]$.

Considering the limited time allocated to EFL curriculum in the Iranian national educational program, and the pressure on the stake holders whose failure or success is measured with the touch-stone of performance on the ECA exams, a deep concern of the teachers, students, and parents, has

almost always been how to devote the available time and energy to the possible classroom tasks and activities to gain the best results on the ECA exams. The results of the present study suggest that the substantial potential of vocabulary learning activities to affect positively the achievement scores must be taken into account in the teaching activities and more emphasis and attention should be given to vocabulary learning, particularly in lower levels of proficiency.

The use of translation in L2 teaching in general- and vocabulary teaching in particular- has been advocated by some prominent scholars of the field (e.g. see G. Cook, 2010, pp.34-35; Howatt and Widdoson, 2004, p.312;Widdowson, 2003, pp. 149-164). It is high time that the applied linguists and language teaching researchers took translation from the ostracism and review its value in language teaching (G Cook, 2010).

In addition, some scholars have expressed doubts concerning the learners' ability in using the knowledge acquired as such in L2 contexts of use. Nevertheless, the findings of the present study showed that this might not be the case. They corroborate the idea that all the mental resources and potentials (one of which is L1) must be harnessed to cope with the gigantic task of second language learning. Moreover, psycholinguistic studies by Jiang (2002) and Sunderman and Kroll (2006) also demonstrate that L1 is simultaneously active during L2 lexical processing in learners notwithstanding their proficiency levels. Although it is quite unfashionable to use L1 in learning and teaching an L2 nowadays, maybe as a result of the remains of the behaviorist psychology and the audio-lingual method once prevailing the field, given the omnipresent nature of L1 influence, it seems perfectly logical to take the most use of it when it is beneficial to us.

There is an extensive body of research which shows a robust relation between vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension. However, the remarkable power of the vocabulary knowledge as the predictor of the learners' success in the End of the Course Achievement (ECA) tests which can somehow be regarded as special measures of proficiency, although, with a narrower scope and more restricted universe of generalizability, implies that this robust relation is probably not limited to reading comprehension only. The ECA tests used in the study included various test sections tapping the writing skill, phonetic and grammatical knowledge, including the reading skill. The high correlation of vocabulary learning and the performance on the ECA tests implies that there might also be strong relations between vocabulary knowledge, syntactic knowledge and the writing skills of the learners. This becomes quite plausible taking into account the fact that lexical knowledge is a multifaceted complex which encompasses a series of component features ranging from semantic features to syntactic, phonetic, orthographic, collocational, and sociolinguistic ones. However, further research is needed to investigate the possible relationships among them.

However, the study was limited only to Intermediate-Mid proficiency level learners and further research is needed to explore the possible patterns of relation between vocabulary learning and proficiency achievement in higher levels of language ability. In addition, no control was made over the moderator variables such as intelligence, language learning aptitude, working-memory, and other individual differences, without a rigorous controlling of which, the results of the study might become difficult for transparent interpretation regarding the underlying factors contributing to the correlation.

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Appendix 1 (Book Three Lexical Items)

Lesson 1 lexical items taught to Grade Three students

Target Words	Persian (Farsi) Translations	Target Words	Persian (Farsi) Translations
allow	اجازه دادن	observation	مشاهده
at the end of	در انتهای	once (a week)	یک بار در هفته
at the front	در مقابل	out at work	بیرون سر کار
average	میانگین	period	دوره
(be) careful about	مراقب بودن در مورد	powerful	قدرتمند
(be) interested in	علاقمند بودن به	practice (n)	تمرین
behave	رفتار کردن	pressure	فشار
case	مورد	probably	احتمالاً
certain	بعرضی	recent	اخیر- جدید
channel	کانال (تلویزیون)	recently	اخیراً
choice	انتخاب ، گزینه	relax	استراحت کردن
choose	انتخاب کردن	relaxed (adj)	آرام
colorful	رنگارنگ	research	تحقیق کردن
continue	ادامه دادن	researcher	محقق
daily	روزانه	single	تنها- مجرد
effect	اثر ، تأثیر	skill	مهارت
end (v)	پایان دادن	sport	ورزش
except (adv)	به جز	stay (at)	ماندن (در)
experiment	آزمایش	struggle (n)	کشمکش
eyesight	دید ، بینایی	successfully	با موفقیت
future	آینده	take a test	امتحان دادن
get...away from	دور کردن از	television set	دستگاه تلویزیون
harmful	مضر	theater	تئاتر
holiday	تعطیلی	twice (a week)	دو بار در هفته
housewife	زن خانه دار	type (n)	نوع ، گونه
How often...?	چند وقت به چند وقت...؟	unusual	غیر معمول
improve	بهبود پیدا کردن	viewer	بیننده
influence	تحت تأثیر قرار دادن	weak	ضعیف
movie	فیلم	wonderful	شگفت انگیز
music	موسیقی	worry about	نگران بودن در مورد

Lesson 2 lexical items taught to Grade Three students

Target Words	Persian (Farsi) Translations	Target Words	Persian (Farsi) Translations
as soon as	به محض اینکه	in other words	به بیانی دیگر
ashamed of	شرمنده از	insist on	اصرار ورزیدن بر
(be) on time	سر وقت (بودن)	lie (v)	دراز کشیدن
blind	نا بینا	means	وسیله، ابزار
clerk	منشی - کارمند	modern	جدید ، پیشرفته
dangerous	خطر ناک	nation	ملت
degree	مدرک علمی - درجه دانشگاهی	passenger	مسافر
discussion	بحث	perfect (adj)	کامل، بی نقص
dislike	دوست نداشتن	possible	ممکن
driving test	امتحان رانندگی	prepare	آماده کردن
educate	آموزش دادن	produce	تولید کردن
end (n)	هدف	rapidly	سریع - به سرعت
examine	بررسی کردن	realize	پی بردن
fact	واقعیت	refuse	امتناع کردن
fashionable	رایج	role	نقش
fill	پر کردن	rubbish	زباله
final	نهایی	service	خدمات - خدمت
fit	مناسب کردن - آماده نمودن	show (n)	نمایش
flight	پرواز	silly	احمق - کودن
forbid	منع کردن	society	جامعه
free	آزاد - رایگان	stupid	خنک ، ابله ، کم هوش
goal	هدف	take away from	دور کردن از - بیرون بردن از
government	دولت	useful	مفید
honest	صدیق	What time is the film on?	فیلم کی پخش میشود؟
however	اما ، با این وجود	value	ارزش - قدر - بها
in fact	در واقع	whether	چه... - که آیا

Lesson 3 lexical items taught to Grade Three students

Target Words	Persian (Farsi) Translations	Target Words	Persian (Farsi) Translations
ability	توانایی	mental	ذهنی
afraid (of)	نگران (از)	mind (n)	ذهن
amount	مقدار	mistake	اشتباه
area	منطقه	object	شیء ، جسم
basis	مبنا	occur	اتفاق افتادن
brain	مغز	over and over	بصورت مکرر
briefly	به صورت مختصر	over-learning	حفظ کردن، به خاطر سپردن
call up	فرا خواندن	pace	سرعت
chemical	شیمیایی	painful	دردناک
conscious	خود آگاه	photographic	تصویر مانند
dead	مرده ، بی جان	physical	جسمی
detail	جزء ، جزئیات	poem	شعر
emotional	عاطفی	psychologist	روانشناس
enter	وارد شدن به	question (v)	مورد سؤال قرار دادن
even (adj)	یکنواخت	recall	به خاطر آوردن
event	واقعه	record (n , v)	سابقه – ضبط کردن
exist	وجود داشتن	responsible	مسئول
feeling	احساس	scene	صحنه
foreigner	خارجی	search for	جستجو به دنبال
forest	جنگل	shopkeeper	مغازه دار
hear about	شنیدن در باره	slow down	کاهش یافتن
hobby	سرگرمی	sorry about	متأسف برای
information	اطلاعات	stick in one's mind	در ذهن ماندن
interest (n)	علاقه	talk with	حرف زدن با
jet	جت	thus	بنا بر این
look after	مراقبت از	turn up	زیاد کردن (صدا)
loss	از دست دادن	weekend	آخر هفته
memory	حافظه		

Lesson 4 lexical items taught to Grade Three students

Target Words	Persian (Farsi) Translations	Target Words	Persian (Farsi) Translations
and so on	و غیره	length	طول
athlete	ورزشکار	measure (n , v)	مقیاس – اندازه گیری کردن
attract	جذب کردن	medal	مدال
award	هدیه کردن	meeting	جلسه
basically	اساساً	Olympia	کوه المپیا
bathroom	حمام	Olympic	المپیک
bottom	ته ، پائین	Olympics	بازی های المپیک
boxing	بوکس	operate	عمل کردن – کار کردن
bronze	برنز	organize	سازمان دهی کردن
celebration	جشن	pair	جفت ، دو
committee	کمیته	permit (v)	اجازه دادن
competition	مسابقه	place (v)	مقام آوردن
consist of	شامل شدن	plain	صحرا
control	هدایت کردن	play a part in	نقش ایفا کردن در
cycle (v)	دوچرخه سواری کردن	religious	مذهبی
Denmark	دانمارک	serious	جدی
depth	عمق	shelf	طاقچه - طبقه
encourage	تشویق کردن	silently	بی صدا
envelop	پاکت نامه	silver	نقره
force (v)	مجبور کردن	site	محل ، منطقه
fortune	شانس	skating (n)	اسکیت بازی
friendship	دوستی	skiing (n)	اسکی بازی
Greece	یونان	snow – covered	برف پوشیده
gymnastics	ژیمناستیک	so far	تا به حال
heat (n)	گرما	take part in	شرکت کردن در
height	ارتفاع	team	تیم
hold	برگزار کردن	together	کنار هم
ice – hockey	هاکی روی یخ	track and field	دو و میدانی
immediately	فوراً	weekly	هفتگی
include	شامل شدن	width	پهنا
individual	فرد ، شخص	win	برنده شدن
instruction	راهنما – دستورالعمل	winner	برنده
international	بین المللی	wrestle	کشتی گرفتن
lake	دریاچه	wrestling	کشتی

Lesson 5 lexical items taught to Grade Three students

Target Words	Persian (Farsi) Translations	Target Words	Persian (Farsi) Translations
after a while	پس از مدتی	involve	در برداشتن
amused (adi)	سرگرم	Iran Air	شرکت ایران ایر
amusing (adj)	سرگرم کننده	instead (of)	به جای
behind	پشت	keep accounts	حسابداری کردن
bored (adj)	کسل	long ago	سالها قبل
boring	کسل کننده	make up	ساختن
call out	فریاد زدن	manage	توانستن – مدیریت کردن
carpet	فرش	meal	غذا
company	شرکت ، کمپانی	Moslem	مسلمان
confused (adj)	گیج	papyrus	کاغذ پاپیروس
contusing (adj)	گیج کننده	report (n)	گزارش
cotton	پنبه	sheet	برگه ، صفحه ، ورق
Egypt	مصر	shocked (adj)	شوکه شده
exciting	هیجان انگیز	shocking (adj)	ترس آور
excited (adj)	هیجان زده	shout (v)	فریاد زدن
far apart	دور از هم	smell (v)	بوئیدن
fear	ترس	surprised (adj)	متعجب
fast (n , v)	روزه ، روزه گرفتن ، ناشتا ماندن	surprising (adj)	تعجب آور
frightened (adj)	ترسیده	taste (v)	چشیدن
habit	عادت	up and down	فراز و نشیب
hard working	سخت کوش	whenever	هر وقت
How do you do?	حال شما چگونه؟	wire (n)	سیم ، خط (تلفن)
invent	اختراع کردن		
invention	اختراع		

Lesson 6 lexical items taught to Grade Three students

Target Words	Persian (Farsi) Translations	Target Words	Persian (Farsi) Translations
action	عمل ، کار	influence (v)	تحت تأثیر قرار دادن
activity	فعالیت	inform	اطلاع دادن
airline	شرکت هواپیمایی	on your left	سمت چپ تان
aspect	بعد ، وجه	orbit (v)	چرخیدن

available	در دسترس	otherwise	در غیر اینصورت
by means of	به وسیله	perform	اجرا کردن
block	مجتمع ساختمانی ، بلوک	pocket - sized	اندازه جیبی
capacity	ظرفیت	process (v)	پردازش کردن
central	مرکزی	programmable	برنامه پذیر
chemist	شیمی دان	project (n)	پروژه
come in	تولید شدن	properly	به صورت شایسته
constantly	به صورت مستمر	research (v)	تحقیق کردن
deny	انکار کردن	right - hand side	سمت راست
design (v)	طراحی کردن	separate (adj)	مجزاً
designer	طراح	series	سری ها
disabled (adj)	معلول ، ناتوان	spacecraft	فضا پیما
drug	دارو	success	موفقیت
endeavor	تلاش	superhuman	ابر بشر
entertainment	سرگرمی	switch (v)	تغییر وضعیت دادن
exactly	دقیقاً	task	وظیفه
furthermore	ضمناً	tower	برج ، ساختمان بلند
giant	غول پیکر	turn (v)	چرخیدن
go straight on	مستقیم برو جلو	turning	چرخش
handle (v)	مواجه شدن	wind power	نیروی باد
in addition to	علاوه بر		

Appendix 2 (Vocabulary Tests Administered to Grade Three Learners)

Vocabulary Test from L1 Grade Three

Supply the English Equivalent(s) of the Meanings Given in Persian and Write the Pronunciation of the English Words in Persian Transcript.

Meaning	English Equivalent(s)	Pronunciation
اجازه دادن		
علاقمند بودن به		
انتخاب ، گزینه		
اثر ، تأثیر		
آینده		
چند وقت به چند وقت....؟		
مشاهده		
شگفت انگیز		
احتمالاً		
استراحت کردن		

Vocabulary Test from L2 Grade Three

Supply the English Equivalent(s) of the Meanings Given in Persian and Write the Pronunciation of the English Words in Persian Transcript.

Meaning	English Equivalent(s)	Pronunciation
شرمنده از		
مدرک علمی- درجه دانشگاهی		
بررسی کردن		
رایج		
دولت		
چه - که آیا		
خنگ ، ابله ، کم هوش		
زیاله		
امتناع کردن		
سریع - به سرعت		

Vocabulary Test from L3 Grade Three

Supply the English Equivalent(s) of the Meanings Given in Persian and Write the Pronunciation of the English Words in Persian Transcript.

Meaning	English Equivalent(s)	Pronunciation
توانایی		
مغز		
مرده ، بی جان		
واقعه		
مراقبت از		
ذهنی		
کاهش یافتن		
روانشناس		
صحنه		
بنا بر این		

Vocabulary Test from L4 Grade Three

Supply the English Equivalent(s) of the Meanings Given in Persian and Write the Pronunciation of the English Words in Persian Transcript.

Meaning	English Equivalent(s)	Pronunciation
ورزشکار		
ته ، پائین		
مسابقه		
عمق		
برگزار کردن		
راهنما - دستورالعمل		
بازی های المپیک		
مقام آوردن		
بی صدا		
دو و میدانی		

Vocabulary Test from L5 Grade Three

Supply the English Equivalent(s) of the Meanings Given in Persian and Write the Pronunciation of the English Words in Persian Transcript.

Meaning	English Equivalent(s)	Pronunciation
سر گرم کننده		
فرش		
مصر		
روزه ، روزه گرفتن ، ناشتا ماندن		
اختراع کردن		
حسابداری کردن		
مسلمان		
متعجب		
هر وقت		
برگه ، صفحه ، ورق		

Vocabulary Test from L6Grade Three

Supply the English Equivalent(s) of the Meanings Given in Persian and Write the Pronunciation of the English Words in Persian Transcript.

Meaning	English Equivalent(s)	Pronunciation
فعالیت		
به وسیله		
شیمی دان		
طراحی کردن		
تلاش		
فضا پیما		
چرخیدن		
مجزاً		
اطلاع دادن		
در غیر اینصورت		

Appendix 3 (End of the Course Achievement (ECA) Test Used for Grade Three)

باسمه تعالی		
سؤالات امتحان نهایی درس: زبان انگلیسی (۳)	کلیه رشته ها	ساعت شروع: ۸ صبح
سال سوم آموزش متوسطه	تاریخ امتحان: ۳۱ / ۳ / ۱۳۸۷	مدت امتحان: ۱۱۰ دقیقه
دانش آموزان و داوطلبان آزاد سراسر کشور در نوبت دوم (خرداد ماه) سال ۱۳۸۷	اداره کل سنجش و ارزشیابی تحصیلی	
ردیف	سؤالات	نمره
۱	<p>توجه: لطفاً تمام پاسخ ها را در پاسخنامه به ترتیب شماره بنویسید.</p> <p>کلمات ناقص را به طور کامل باز نویسی کنید.</p> <p>A.B. Students should be ash – med of doing s – lly things in the classroom.</p> <p>C.D. Dinner times were more r – laxed without the press – re of TV.</p> <p>E.F. Psycholo – ists believe that forget – ing does not take place at an even pace.</p> <p>G.H. He remembers in great d – tails, objects or sc – nes he has looked at only briefly.</p> <p>I. J. We want to solve all the problems of so – iety and make a p – rf – ct nation.</p> <p>K. L. A lot of vie – ers follow their countries' fo – tunes on TV.</p> <p>M. N. The Olympics attra – t a lot of people and c – nsist of winter and summer games.</p> <p>O. P. No one can d – ny the importance of computers in any f – – ld of endeavour.</p>	4
۲	<p>با استفاده از کلمات داده شده جمله های زیر را کامل کنید. (یک کلمه اضافی است.)</p> <p>choice – celebration – shouted – emotional – orbit – recall – separate – average – realized</p> <p>1. Her was very low. She studied harder and improved it.</p> <p>2. My friend likes to have a great on her birthday.</p> <p>3. I want to buy a book for my little son. Can you help me to make a good ?</p> <p>4. I can still the hard work that I had to do when I was a worker.</p> <p>5. When I saw your son in the deep part of the sea, I for help.</p> <p>6. Parents should know that children have both physical and needs.</p> <p>7. Finally the police that the two boys were lying.</p> <p>8. My sisters sleep together, but my brother and I have rooms.</p>	4
۳	<p>شکل صحیح کلمات داخل پرانتز را در جاهای خالی بنویسید.</p> <p>9. The cinema was empty, so I could find a seat . (easy)</p> <p>10. I accepted their to have lunch with them . (invite)</p> <p>11. You should try to be a member of your country. (use)</p> <p>12. I didn't understand the film because it was very..... (confuse)</p> <p>13. My friend can swim the of the pool several times. (long)</p> <p>14. He looks , but can we employ him? (honest)</p>	3
۴	<p>جمله های زیر را فقط با نوشتن <u>یک کلمه ی مناسب</u> کامل کنید.</p> <p>15. Overlearning makes things in your mind.</p> <p>16. Something that you enjoy doing in your free time is called your</p> <p>17. Computers do their jobs by means of processing the</p> <p>18. A bronze medal is given to the third – place in every competition.</p> <p>19. We went to the, but the plane arrived two hours late.</p> <p>20. Watching too much TV may have a bad on children's eyesight.</p>	3
«ادامه ی سؤالات در صفحه ی دوم»		

باسمه تعالی

مدت امتحان : ۱۱۰ دقیقه	ساعت شروع : ۸ صبح	کلیه رتبه ها	سوالات امتحان نهایی درس : زبان انگلیسی (۳)
تاریخ امتحان : ۱۳۸۷ / ۳ / ۲۱		سال سوم آموزش متوسطه	
اداره کل سنجش و ارزشیابی تحصیلی		دانش آموزان و داوطلبان آزاد سراسر کشور در نوبت دوم (خرداد ماه) سال ۱۳۸۷	

ردیف	سوالات	نمره
۵	پاسخ صحیح را از بین گزینه های داده شده انتخاب کنید. 21. We walked very carefully along the snow – covered street. We were afraid falling. a. from b. of c. on d. for 22. My mother disliked me with impolite boys. a. sees b. saw c. see d. seeing 23. Reza has decided to go shopping. He something for dinner. a. has bought b. is going to buy c. had to buy d. would buy 24. " Where do they visit him ?" "I don't know where him." a. do they visit b. did they visit c. they visit d. they visited 25. "Did you call up their son?" "No, I didn't call " a. him up b. up them c. them up d. up him 26. These Japanese cars since 1998. a. haven't used b. didn't use c. haven't been used d. weren't used	3
۶	با هر گروه از کلمات زیر یک جمله ی کامل بنویسید. 27. names – on this page – be – their – written – must . 28. cotton – his – is wearing – shirt – white – he – new .	2
۷	بر اساس جمله ها ی داده شده جملات ناقص را کامل کنید. 29. Is it important for you to answer this letter? Yes, answering 30. The teacher told me, "Don't talk with your friends." The teacher told me	2
۸	با توجه به تصاویر به سوالات زیر پاسخ کامل دهید. 31. What did Mr Salehi advise him to do ? 	2
«ادامه ی سوالات در صفحه ی سوم»		

